

Impact Of Abusive Supervision And Feedback Avoidance On Employee Creativity With Mediated And Moderated Effect In A Private School System

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 20, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Abusive Supervision, Feedback Avoidance, Interactional Justice, Employee Creativity</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5148781</p>	<p><i>Abuse of supervision is a well-documented phenomenon with many negative consequences. In recent years, there has been great emphasis on investigations for abuse of control. The main objective of this study is to empirically test the impact of monitoring abuse and to avoid comments on the honesty and creativity of employees in the private school system. Using quantitative methods, 250 teachers working in schools in Rawalpindi and Islamabad were interviewed on a structured questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale. SPSS version 21 is used for correlation and regression analysis. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is used to assess factors, while structural equation modeling (SEM) is used to test hypotheses, using AMOS version 22. Regression analysis and confirmatory factor analysis verify that the hypothetical model is the most appropriate model. These results indicate that the abuse of supervision is the main source of stress which reduces creativity, pointing out that it reduces creativity, and avoiding feedback also has a negative effect on reducing creativity. This relationship has a partial mediating effect between teachers thus negatively affecting their interaction and fairness in the workplace. This ultimately leads to compromising mutual emotional cooperation which can bring greater benefit to them and to the organization.</i></p>

Introduction

Employee creativity is seen as an important part of the instructional endurance and efficiency (Shalley, Zhou & Oldham, 2004). Creation refers to a new product, practice, service or process that is useful in the workplace (Amabil, 1996). The educational standards accepted by students eventually declined, teachers felt underrepresented and the teacher-student relationship was compromised, as a result, the school environment has deteriorated (Ozkilic & Kartal, 2012). Teachers' creativity, material designing and student participation also decreases. They switch to a teacher-centered approach that reduces practice and preparation processes (Blase & Blase, 2006).

Wet and L. Jacobs (2010) research work studies the impact of understanding and reluctance in teacher student relationship (Blase & Blase, 2004; Ozkilic & Kartal, 2012). The relationship and collaboration with the teacher was mainly broken by public intimidation (De Wet, 2010). Employee creativity is an indispensable part of innovation, including the generation of new ideas, as well as the implementation of these new ideas (Shalley et al., 2004; Zhou, 2003).

Employee creativity is a unique activity which is the necessary component of innovation creativity (Joo, McLean & Yang, 2013). That's the reason for getting support by maximum researchers and practitioners. Present study has focused on abusive supervision and examine the dark side of the leadership, defined as the perception of subordinates' involvement in the leader's persistent verbal and non-verbal aggressive behavior.

Language does not involve physical contact (Tipper, 2000). Abusive supervision has many causes like when organizational leaders have high power and when they are controlling their stakes which is more likely to abuse supervision (Tepper, Carl, Breo, Gade, Hu Yuhua, 2009). Empirical evidence shows abusive supervision that can have serious negative effects on health for example: anxiety, aggression, stress, resistance and unemployment (Martinko, Harvey, Brees, Mackey, 2013). Functional feedback refers to the extent to which the activities required to perform their jobs lead to people receiving direct and clear information about the effectiveness of their performance (Hackman et al. Oldham, 1976). Trying out new ideas can obviously only be seen when employees whose ideas are not innovative can emerge and as a result experience emotions which are negatively affected to emotions that destroy their motivation, reduce their sense of identity (LuSaavedra & Kwun, 2000). Feedback Avoidance is considered a precursor to the sensory process. Supervisors can use avoidance of feedback to shape how employees understand their mistakes and to readjust attitudes, feelings, or behaviors that may be counterproductive to employees and the organization (Ford, 1996). People are increasingly interested in understanding how to increase creativity in organizations (Zhou & Shalley, 2008; Shalley et al., 2004), which is

defined as the generation of new and useful ideas (Amabile, 1996), which considers sustainable competitive advantage (George, 2007). Unsurprisingly, researchers have invested a lot of work in studying related psychological forces. Intrinsic motivation has become one of these cores and can encourage employees to use relatively aging commitments for learning and practicing (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Therefore, existing creativity research relies heavily on self-motivation (Amabile, 1996). However, research on the intrinsic motivational connection of creativity has produced clear results (George, 2007). Most studies have shown that self-motivation leads to higher levels of creativity (Janssen and Van, 2004; Shin and Zhou, 2003), as organizational psychologists and researchers have long expected. At the same time, more and more evidence shows that there is no significant correlation between self-motivation and creativity (Smith, 2006).

Perceived interactive justice applies to the sense of justice in the interpersonal communication of the leaders' subordinates who perform formal procedures (Bies and Shapiro, 1987). This reflects how subordinates treat them with sincerity, fairness, respect and dignity (Bies & Moag, 1986). Perceiving interactive justice can be an important psychological process. It explains the influence of the three dimensions of paternalistic leadership on the work behavior of subordinates for two reasons. First, the perceived fairness of interaction has been shown to be related to employees' evaluation of their managers (Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter & Ng, 2001), and the distribution of key performance variables and the perceived fairness process. (Cropanzano, Préhar). & Chen, 2002). Second, perceived interactive justice has been promoted and verified in various cultural backgrounds including Pakistan (Farh, Earley & Lin, 1997). Using interaction fairness as an important communication variable, researchers can explore whether the relationship between creativity and violent supervision will have a unique impact on employees working in private schools.

The world has become a global village and business survival requires a better understanding of quality management practices. The innovation or creativity of the employees is seen as a key factor of concerning the status in the international market. The need to follow the demanding and constantly evolving global model and its standards. Human resources are very important for any organization, especially to gain a competitive advantage on a global scale (Devi & Pojitha 2012). The current research focuses on the internal customers of the organisation, i.e. the employees. The private school sector is described as a more demanding industry. Because of work, employees may have to put up with longer working hours, high pressure and work pressure. There are approximately 301 national and international private schools (ilm.com.pk) in Pakistan. There are currently around 31 private schools in Islamabad and around 17 private schools in Peshawar (ilm.com.pk). Pakistan is one of the most populous regions and majority population is living below the poverty line. Therefore, Pakistani government supports other private school organizations in to meet some of the basic needs like illiteracy, health issues and many other grave issues. These private schools in Pakistan are mainly dedicated to improving women's education and environment in Pakistan. These private schools are always ready to help those in need (Brown & David, 2009).

This research aims to determine the misuse of supervision and avoidance of comments from the Pakistani private school sector and its impact on employee creativity using fairness in interaction as a mediating and motivating variable. Inherent as a moderate variant. This phenomenon negatively affects the well-being of employees and the entire organization. This survey will help private school administrators enhance interpersonal communication so that employees can discuss ideas, issues, and important information with supervisors in a timely manner. Few studies have tested the effect of observation and the abuse of feedback on creativity through the mediating role of responsive justice. This contributes to the theoretical contribution of the literature. This study will explore in depth the mediating role of intrinsic motivation in the above relationship.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Supporting Theories

There are two theories related to this research study. The first one is Conservative Resource Theory and the second one is Justice Perception Theory. Resource Conservation Theory (RCT) is a stress theory (Hobfoll, 1989), which explains the impact and management of stress in life. In this theory, a resource refers to any thing, quality, condition, or appearance that is valuable to a person. Leader abuse can also reflect leadership behavior when resources are exhausted (Byrne et al., 2014). Resource conservation theory (RCT) (Hobfoll, 2001) has been used to explain negative management results. The RCT theory predicts that people who lack personal resources will experience stress and lose more resources. People strive to preserve and protect certain valuable psychological characteristics, objects, energies and relationships (Hobfoll, 1989, 2001).

According to the scientific literature of the organization, fairness plays an important role in the effectiveness of the organization. Colckett et al. (2001). Organizational justice is the fair treatment of workers in the workplace and the impact of their opinions on other work-related variables Moorman (1991). The theory of justice involves a person's assessment of the fairness of an organization. By following ethical standards, people believe that their treatment in the organization is fair, consistent, and predictable (Krupanzana, Bowen, and Gilliland, 2007). Conservation resource theory is representing different impressions of abusive supervision on employees, while justice perception theory is representing interactional justice in this study. Based on the conservation of

resource theory by Hobfall (1989), which states that everyone looks to preserve resources like objects and energy. Stress happens when resources drop, which leads to job dissatisfaction and one consider quitting a job. Hence in accordance with that, the resources which can be used in exploratory behaviors such as creativity become limited.

To obtain a competitive advantage, the creativity of employees is used as the basis for organizational innovation (George, 2007; Zhang & Bartol, 2010). Personal creativity is often described as a key factor in fostering organizational innovation (Amabile, 1988; Woodman, Sawyer, & Griffen, 1993). Personal creativity generally means implementing creative ideas, which is important to the survival and long-term success of the organization. This is very important (Kanter, 1983; Utterback, 1994; Amabile et al., 1996; Tushman and Reilly, 1997). However, creativity is a complex structure, so it is difficult to define it. There is no general agreement on the definition, but a consistent concept can be found in the current definition. Guilford (1950) believed that "the creator has new ideas" and would give "unusual but acceptable answers." Similarly, Sternberg and Lobart (1999) have emphasized that creativity is "the ability to create work that is new (that is, original and unexpected) and appropriate (that is, useful and adaptable to constraints of the task)". Also, Barron and Haring Dayton (1981) use words like "grandmother", "original" and "powerful" to define creativity. Finally, Martindale (1989) believes that creativity "must be original, it must be useful or appropriate to the situation, and it must be really used." Given the themes common to these definitions, the value of creativity in organizations seems to be related to the development of new and appropriate ones. The idea is related to the ability to improve organizational efficiency, solve complex problems, and improve overall efficiency.

2.3 Abusive Supervision

So far, a lot has been done with constructive leadership and its impact on the attitudes, performance, and well-being of employees. Anrod et al. (2007). On the other hand, supervisory abuse is a destructive leadership structure, including temperament, angry behavior, and invasion of privacy, lies, successful appointment of subordinates, general mockery, and expressions of anger towards subordinates.

Started in 2000. Tepper (2000) defines violent surveillance as the perception of "subordinates", that is, their superiors continue to show hostile verbal and nonverbal behavior to prevent contact. After Tepper's extensive work, several studies were conducted to investigate the negative effects of surveillance abuse, its impact on employees, and subsequent organizational results. It is manifested in the poor performance of individuals and teams (Priesemuth, Schminke, Ambrose & Folger, 2014), counterproductive work behavior, poor attitudes towards work and employee organization, Tepper (2000) and family conflicts in the workplace (Hoobler & Brass, 2006). Mental stress and reluctance to help (Peng, Schaubroeck, and Li, 2014) reduce employee satisfaction (Lian, Ferisa, and Brown, 2012). (Tepper, 2007) pointed out that illegal surveillance of the organization costs money. For example, approximately 14% of employees in the United States have experienced management abuse, causing the company to spend approximately \$24 billion annually on excessive vacations, lost productivity, and health care costs. Poor performance in official performance reviews (Harris, Kacmar, and Zivnuska, 2007). Negative awakening has been the subject of research for a long time. Originally called Supervisor Barrier (Duffy, Granster & Pagon, 2002) and Supervisor Aggression (Treasure, Desmarais & Kelloway, 2006), this design meets the needs of violent surveillance and has received the most attention and workload. In the past 15 years, a wide range of theoretical fields have been involved. This includes the relationship between violent surveillance and important organizational results, such as aggressiveness (Burton & Hoobler, 2011), bad organizational social behavior (Rafferty & Restubog, 2011), poor performance (Tepper, Mossand Duffy, 2011), and Professional bias. (Mitchell & Ambrose, 2007).

2.5 Feedback Avoidance

Newly launched products often fails and the major reason is defects, as per survey conducted less than 60% of the products survive and remaining can be successful even in lessor number (Castellion and Markham, 2013), which is around 25% (Evanschitzky, Eisend, Calantone & Jiang, 2012). Innovative work often involves risk, so innovators who bring new products to market may encounter errors at some point in the process of conceptualization, realization and production. Job feedback is "the degree to which performing the work activities required for the job enables individuals to immediately obtain clear information about performance effectiveness" (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Obviously, innovative employees who try out new ideas find that their ideas have failed and they will get negative feedback at work. As a result, they can experience negative emotions, which can weaken their motivation, reduce their sense of self-efficacy and make them frustrated and anxious (Lubart, 2001; Saavedra & Kwun, 2000).

Why do innovative employees persevere despite consistently negative results? Personality plays an important role (Prabhu, Sutton & Sauser, 2008; Sternberg, 2006), but managers can have a significant impact on the persistence of creative employees in creative work, depending on how the manager delivers. Negative feedback. Again, the construction of meaning is a feedback process (Weick, 1993). It is a cognitive activity which explains and constructs life situations. It is a process of making sense of external experiences and stimuli. The importance of creation is continuous and recurring, so collaborators can educate themselves while responding to false feedback. Especially when supervisors evaluate employee performance, ideally the feedback will motivate

employees to work more efficiently (Chen & Huang, 2009; Jiménez & Valle, 2005; Noefer, Stegmaier, Molter & Sonntag, 2009). However, little is known about the specific ways in which managers provide false feedback without affecting employees.

2.6 Interactive Justice

Interaction fairness is the quality of interpersonal management accepted by individuals (Folger & Cropanzano, 1998). People tend to connect with others and worry about how others will treat themselves. When employees are treated without dignity or respect, when their personal needs are ignored or when their treatment violates certain formal rules, unfair interactions occur (Bies & Moag, 1986; Lamertz, 2002); Niehov & Moormann, 1993). Previous studies have shown that abuse of surveillance is a strong predictor of injustice (eg, Tepper, 2000; Zellars et al., 2002). Interactive justice describes the quality of treatment that employees receive in the workplace (Pace, 2005). Researchers note that managers play a key role in managing justice in the workplace, especially interactive justice (Scott, Garza, Conlon & Kim, 2014). The supervisor is primarily responsible for providing an ethical and safe environment in the organization (Sheen, 2012). It is clear from the definition of the abuse of surveillance that it violates the normative rules of justice (Tepper, 2000). Personally, I intend to question the person responsible for the perceived injustice, and to find the perpetrators in the perceptual injustice. First, employees can report their unfair treatment to their immediate supervisor (Ayree et. Al 2007); Burton and Hepler, 2011; Tepper, 2000). Second, he beat up subordinate superiors for neglecting them in the workplace. Zelis et al. (2002). This research focuses on the first idea that supervisors who experience unfair interactions exhibit more violent behavior towards their employees. (Ari, Chen, Sun & Debra, 2007).

2.7 The relationship between censorship abuse, creativity and avoidance of feedback

Abuse of supervision is defined as the subordinate's perception of the degree to which superiors continue to exhibit aggressive verbal and nonverbal behavior, in addition to physical contact (Tepper, 2000). Direct observation of violence is similar to the concept of emotional abuse proposed by Keashly et al. (1994), that is, emotional abuse refers to one or more hostile verbal and nonverbal behavior towards another person, in addition to physical contact. According to Keashly and Harvey Keashly et al. (2005) in the workplace, a person may experience constant disdain from some colleagues or supervisors. Recent researches suggest that employees do not have sufficient status to investigate, and even if they have new ideas, they will not receive material resources or support (Gu, Tang & Jiang, 2015). The abuse of surveillance can also be considered a particularly harmful form. This can lead to inconsistencies between circumstances, leading to increased avoidance of feedback, and previous research has shown that this harms creativity and prevents feedback (Bay et al., 2000).

2.8 The relationship between censorship abuse, creativity, feedback and the mediating role of interactive justice

According to Bies and Moag (1986), mutual justice refers to the quality of interpersonal communication that employees experience during the implementation of a program. In particular, Colquitt (2001) identifies the extent to which employees believe they are respectful, polite, and free from inappropriate or destructive comments in personal interactions. Tepper (2000) found that abuse of surveillance can have a negative impact on the sense of justice, including reactive justice, procedural justice, and distributive justice. In this study, since interaction fairness is considered a mediating variable of interaction fairness, it can support the negative consequences of supervisor abuse and its negative impact on employee creativity. . These circumstances lead to the following assumptions: Tepper coined the term violent surveillance in 2000. Tepper (2000) defines violent surveillance as the perception of “subordinates” to the extent that his superiors continue to exhibit verbal and nonverbal hostile behavior, except for contact. Following Tepper's extensive work, several studies have been conducted to examine the harmful effects of perceived supervisory abuse, its effect on employees, and subsequent organizational outcomes. This manifests itself in poor personal and group performance (Priesemuth, Schminke, Ambrose & Folger, 2014).

2.10 Theoretical Model

Theoretical model of the study is shown in the figure 2.1.

2.10 Hypotheses

Below are the hypothesis of the study:

- H₁: There is significant and negative impact of abusive supervision on employee creativity.
- H₂: There is significant and negative impact of feedback avoidance on employee creativity.
- H₃: There is significant impact of abusive supervision and interactional Justice.
- H₄: There is significant impact of Feedback avoidance and Interactional Justice.
- H₅: There is the significant impact of Interactional Justice and employee creativity.
- H₆: Interactional Justice has mediating effect between abusive supervision and employee creativity.
- H₇: Interactional Justice has mediating effect between feedback avoidance and employee creativity.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Population of the Study

The research team is divided into groups of people or projects with similar characteristics (Castello, 2009). Residents in this study are considered to be employees of several national and cross-border private schools in two cities in Pakistan (i.e. Rawalpindi and Islamabad). The private school sector is seen as a more demanding industry. Employees may need to work for a long time, the pressure at work is high, and the nature of the work causes pressure.

3.2 Sampling method and sample size

The sampling technique used is intentional sampling and impossible sampling. In this type of sampling, employees who work in private schools, are abused or are employed are selected as study participants. Conscious sampling is used because it saves time and is generally a less expensive method of collecting data. In order to achieve accurate results or the lowest error rate, the minimum number of exams will be around 170-200, so Levine and Stephan (2009) require 250 exams during the exam activity.

3.3 Unit of analysis

An important part of empirical research is the unit of analysis. Each member of an organization is called a unit, and an element of a group is called a unit of analysis. In this document, the unit of analysis includes several employees from the private school sector in Pakistan, with a focus on Islamabad and Peshawar. For this purpose, secondary data was collected from selected private schools in Islamabad and Peshawar.

3.3 Data collection tools

The data collection tool for this study is to distribute the questionnaire to those in the sample who completed the questionnaire based on their opinions on each statement in the questionnaire. The quiz includes scales to build strength, mismanagement, avoid feedback, self-motivation, and fairness in responses.

3.4 Data analysis

The research analysis is descriptive which includes tables and graphs of collected data, i.e. responses obtained using frequency tables and graphs. In addition, a correlation and regression matrix is included in the psychoanalysis to determine the different relationships between the research variables.

Data Collection

The research methods detailed above involve the whole process by which researchers solve the problems raised in the research questions. The target audience for this study are private schools in Pakistan. The data comes from the twin cities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Data was obtained from private schools with permission from Pakistan. The questionnaire was developed using previously validated tools and used in the natural environment of the organization. Coding of development tools (questionnaire). The statistical equation (Krejcie and Morgan, 2005) consists of calculating the largest sample, used to calculate the number of respondents in the general population, with an error rate of 3.5%, a confidence level of 96, 5% and a selection interval of 250 interviews. .

Data analysis and results

SPSS and AMOS are the two most popular data analysis software packages. SPSS is “Social Science Statistics Package” and AMOS is “Analysis of the Structure of the Moment”. The main difference between the two packages is that SPSS is typically used for statistical analysis, while AMOS is used for model fit statistics. SPSS is used to create spreadsheets based on the data collected for the target population of the study. The direct and indirect effects are used to accept the hypothesis of a significance level of 0.05. Structural equation modeling is one of the most primitive techniques in path analysis. Knowledge management and organizational culture with moderate impact have been shown to have a positive impact on competitive advantage. The general model is sufficient and all values are within acceptable ranges. So It is found that H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄, H₅ and H₆ are compatible.

Regarding the alternative hypothesis H1, the results of this study show that there is a significant positive correlation between review abuse and JI. In addition, the correlation coefficient between the two constructs also showed a positive correlation and a significant correlation, with an r value of 0.49 and a p value of <0.05 . In addition, the coefficient β of the relationship between abuse of supervision and YI is 0.78, $p < 0.05$, indicating that the mutual fairness of abuse of supervision is the key to one aspect and occupies an important position in it. This shows that companies need to carefully manage abuse in order to achieve fair interaction, enhance employee creativity, and ultimately promote organizational growth. The results of this study have been validated and supported because they are consistent with the results of previous studies (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2015; Buckley & Caple, 2009).

Table 1: Summary of Hypotheses results H1-H5

Connection Between Variables	Beta value	Critical Value	P value	Decision / Remarks
β_1 (IJ←AS)	0.35	8.22	0.00	Supported
β_2 (IJ← FA)	0.34	7.25	0.00	Supported
β_3 (IJ← EC)	0.41	13.21	0.00	Supported
β_4 (EC← AS)	-0.78	18.21	0.00	Supported
β_5 (EC← FA)	-0.85	21.29	0.00	Supported

Note AS= Abusive Supervision , FA = Feedback Avoidance, EC = Employee Creativity, IJ = Interactional Justice

Mediation Analysis

The data further analyzes the mediating role of interactive justice (Table 2). According to the suggested relationship, assume that H7 is as shown in the figure. The analysis of intermediate effects is based on the method of Barron and Kenny (1986). As reported by Ng et al. It is recommended to use the SPSS guided technique (Preacher & Hayes, 2008) to verify the results by plotting 5,000 samples and a 95% confidence interval (Table 2). (2014). Statistical analysis of the proposed H8 hypothesis shows that reciprocal justice (IJ) significantly mediates the significant relationship between supervisory abuse and employee creativity, so the beta coefficient = 0.595 and $p = 0.001$. Based on the median effect, the IJ β coefficient between AS and EC is 0.261, and a significance level of 0.00 indicates that it is still significant, but the β factor has decreased. This shows that even after entering the median variable factor = 0.334 and p -value = 0.002, the indirect effect is still significant. This confirms that IJ plays an intermediate role in the relationship between AS and EC, thus

partially accepting Hypothesis H7. Similarly, IJ plays another intermediate role in FA-IJ-EC, as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Mediator Model

Variable	Total Effect (C)	Direct effect (C')	Indirect effect (ab)	Result	Mediation level
AS-IJ-EC	$\beta = .595$ $p = 0.001$	$\beta = .261$ $p = 0.00$	$\beta = .334$ $p = 0.002$	Significant	Partial
FA-IJ-EC	$\beta = .351$ $p = 0.002$	$\beta = .124$ $p = 0.022$	$\beta = .226$ $p = 0.00$	Significant	Partial

AS = Abusive Supervision, IJ= Interactional Justice , EC= Employee Creativity , FA= Feedback Avoidance
*** $p \leq 0.05$

Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations. For example, this study covers a limited population, i.e the focus of this study is on the private school sector in Pakistan, in particular all national and transnational private schools operating in Peshawar and Islamabad will serve as the study population. The type of data is also important. In addition, the research is based on cross-sectional properties, so common methodological biases are probable. Longitudinal research requires more time and resources, but the usual method is less likely to deviate.

Conclusion

The bottom line is that the abuse of supervision and the avoidance of feedback have a positive effect on the creativity of employees. At the same time, some people think that employees are an important part of this type of creativity and must consciously look for ways to achieve it successfully. Analysis of this research suggests that the abuse of supervision and the avoidance of feedback are powerful features of creative success. Interactive justice is also a very important part. It must occupy a dominant position in the school system, otherwise creativity must not appear and must be effectively implemented in order to motivate and satisfy the creativity of the employees of the private school system.

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